

Supplementary Fig. S4 DH plants derived from KS13H9 x SY Monument determined as **normal** based on **digital karyotyping (left)**. Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the Jagger reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for KS13H9 (red) and SYMonument (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle. and, **FISH (right)**

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0001-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

Total chromosomes : 42

Supplementary Fig. S4 DH plants derived from KS13H9 x SY Monument determined as **abnormal** based on **digital karyotyping (left)**. Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the Jagger reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for KS13H9 (red) and SYMonument (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle. and, **FISH (right)**

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0009-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	1	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41
- One copy of 1A

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0020-4

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	1+1	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41 + 1
- 1/3 del of the long arm of 2A, arrow

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0012-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	1	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	1
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes : 40
- One copy of 3B
- One copy of 5D

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	1	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	3	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	1
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes : 41
- One copy of 1A
- Three copies of 4B
- One copy of 6D

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0027-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	1
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes : 41
- One copy of 4D

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0033-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	1
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes : 41
- One copy of 3D

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0005-4

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	1
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes : 41
- One copy of 2D

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0009-5

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	1	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes : 41
- One copy of 6B

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0040-4

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	1

- Total chromosomes : 41
- One copy of 7D

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0023-5

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	1+1	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41+1
- Isochromosome 1BS-1BS, arrow

KS13H9SYMonumentDH0018-4

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	1+1	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41+1
- Isochromosome 1BS-1BS, arrow